

Comparison between behavioural therapy & pharmacotherapy in children with ADHD

Dr SHIRDINATH E.R, MBBS,

final yr postgraduate in paediatrics, Meenakshi medical college hospital and research institute, kanchipuram, 631552, Tamilnadu , India

Dr KUMARAN S S , DCH, DNB IN PAEDIATRICS , HOD AND PROFF IN PAEDIATRICS, Meenakshi medical college hospital and research institute, kanchipuram, 631552, Tamilnadu , India

Dr SUDHARSAN N.E, MD PAEDIATRICS, ASST PROFF IN PAEDIATRICS, Meenakshi medical college hospital and research institute, kanchipuram, 631552, Tamilnadu , India

ABSTRACT

Introduction:

Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) is a common neurodevelopmental disorder affecting children, leading to significant impairment in academic, behavioural, and social functioning. Both behavioural therapy and pharmacotherapy are widely used treatment modalities; however, their comparative effectiveness remains a subject of ongoing debate.

Materials and Methods:

This prospective comparative study was conducted from March 2025 to February 2026 at a tertiary care rural hospital in South India. A total of 100 children aged 5–15 years diagnosed with ADHD were included and divided into two groups: behavioural therapy (n=50) and pharmacotherapy (n=50). Behavioural and attention outcomes were assessed using the Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ) and Conners' Parent Rating Scale-Revised (CPRS-R) at baseline and after 12 weeks. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 25.0, with $p < 0.05$ considered significant.

Results:

Baseline characteristics and scores were comparable between the groups ($p > 0.05$). Both interventions showed significant improvement in SDQ and CPRS scores ($p < 0.05$). The mean SDQ score reduced from 22.4 ± 3.8 to 16.2 ± 3.1 in the behavioural therapy group and from 23.1 ± 4.1 to 13.4 ± 2.8 in the pharmacotherapy group. CPRS scores decreased

from 71.2 ± 6.5 to 64.8 ± 5.9 and 72.5 ± 7.1 to 60.2 ± 5.4 , respectively. A higher proportion of children in the pharmacotherapy group achieved normal outcome scores.

Conclusion:

Both behavioural therapy and pharmacotherapy were effective in managing ADHD in children, with pharmacotherapy demonstrating superior short-term improvement. Behavioural therapy remains an important adjunct for comprehensive management.

Keywords:

ADHD, Behavioural therapy, Pharmacotherapy, SDQ, CPRS, Children

INTRODUCTION

Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) is one of the most common neurodevelopmental disorders of childhood, characterized by persistent patterns of inattention, hyperactivity, and impulsivity that interfere with functioning or development [1]. It is a chronic condition that often begins in early childhood and may persist into adolescence and adulthood, significantly impacting academic performance, social interactions, and emotional regulation. ADHD is classified into three subtypes—predominantly inattentive, predominantly hyperactive-impulsive, and combined type—based on symptom presentation[2]. The disorder has multifactorial etiology involving genetic, neurobiological, and environmental influences, including prenatal exposure to toxins, low birth weight, and psychosocial stressors.

Globally, ADHD represents a major public health concern due to its high prevalence and associated functional impairment. A large meta-analysis reported a global prevalence of approximately 8% (95% CI: 6–10%) among children, with higher rates observed in males compared to females [3]. Other systematic reviews have reported pooled prevalence estimates ranging from 5% to 7.2% worldwide, highlighting consistency across different populations [4]. ADHD is associated with significant comorbidities such as oppositional defiant disorder, anxiety disorders, and learning disabilities, further increasing the burden on healthcare systems and families [5].

In the Indian context, ADHD prevalence shows considerable variability due to differences in diagnostic criteria, study settings, and assessment tools. A systematic review and meta-analysis reported a pooled prevalence of 7.1% (95% CI: 5.1–9.8%) among children and adolescents in India, which is comparable to global estimates [6].

Individual Indian studies have reported prevalence rates ranging from 6.3% [7] in rural school children to over 11% in certain school-based populations, with a higher prevalence among males and children from lower socioeconomic groups [8]. These findings emphasize the growing burden of ADHD in India and the need for early identification and effective management strategies.

Management of ADHD primarily includes pharmacotherapy, behavioural therapy, or a combination of both approaches. Pharmacological treatment, particularly with stimulant medications such as methylphenidate and non-stimulants like atomoxetine, has been shown to effectively reduce core symptoms of ADHD by modulating neurotransmitter activity in the brain [9,10]. However, concerns regarding adverse effects, long-term safety, and adherence often limit their use. On the other hand, behavioural therapy focuses on modifying maladaptive behaviours through structured interventions such as parent training, classroom management, and cognitive-behavioural techniques. Behavioural interventions are especially beneficial in younger children and in those with mild to moderate symptoms [11].

Despite the availability of multiple treatment modalities, there remains ongoing debate regarding the relative efficacy of behavioural therapy versus pharmacotherapy, particularly in pediatric populations. While pharmacotherapy may offer rapid symptom control, behavioural therapy addresses functional and psychosocial aspects of the disorder, potentially leading to sustained long-term benefits [12]. Comparative studies evaluating these treatment approaches are essential to guide evidence-based clinical decision-making. Therefore, the present study aims to compare the effectiveness of behavioural therapy and pharmacotherapy in children with ADHD, with particular emphasis on symptom improvement, functional outcomes, and overall treatment response.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present prospective comparative study was conducted from January 2025 to December 2025 at a tertiary care rural hospital in South India. The study included children aged 5–15 years diagnosed with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) attending the Paediatric Outpatient and Inpatient Departments during the

study period. Demographic details such as age, gender, socioeconomic status, parental education, and family structure were recorded using a structured proforma.

Clinical history including duration of symptoms, subtype of ADHD, school performance, and family history of behavioural disorders was obtained. A detailed treatment history was noted, and eligible participants were assigned to receive either behavioural therapy or pharmacotherapy based on clinical indication and parental preference.

The sample size was calculated based on previous comparative studies evaluating behavioural therapy and pharmacotherapy in ADHD. The sample size was determined based on previous studies evaluating behavioural therapy in ADHD. A meta-analysis by Fabiano GA et al., demonstrated significant effectiveness with substantial between-group effect size (0.83); hence, a sample of 100 children (50 per group) was considered adequate to detect a statistically significant difference with 80% power and 5% level of significance[13].

A total of 100 children were included in the study and categorised into two groups:

- Group 1: Behavioural Therapy (n=50)
- Group 2: Pharmacotherapy (n=50)

The study was a time-bound prospective comparative study including all eligible participants during the study period.

Inclusion Criteria

- Children aged 5–15 years
- Children diagnosed with ADHD based on DSM-5 criteria
- Children attending paediatric OPD/IPD during the study period
- Newly diagnosed or treatment-naïve ADHD cases
- Children whose parents/guardians provided informed consent

Exclusion Criteria

- Children with comorbid neurodevelopmental disorders (e.g., autism spectrum disorder, intellectual disability)
- Children with chronic neurological or psychiatric illnesses
- Children on prior long-term ADHD treatment
- Children with severe systemic illness
- Children whose parents/guardians did not provide consent

Study Procedure

After obtaining informed consent from parents or guardians, detailed demographic and clinical data were collected using a structured proforma. ADHD diagnosis was confirmed using DSM-5 criteria by a qualified paediatrician/psychiatrist.

Participants were divided into two groups:

- **Behavioural Therapy Group:** Children received structured behavioural interventions including parent training, classroom behaviour modification strategies, and cognitive-behavioural techniques over a period of 12 weeks.
- **Pharmacotherapy Group:** Children received standard pharmacological treatment, primarily methylphenidate or atomoxetine, with dose titration based on clinical response and tolerability.

Behavioural and attention problems were assessed using standardized tools:

- Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ) [14]
- Conners' Parent Rating Scale-Revised (CPRS-R) [15]

Assessments were performed at baseline and at the end of 12 weeks of intervention.

Behavioural Assessment (SDQ):

The Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ) consists of five subscales: emotional symptoms, conduct problems, hyperactivity/inattention, peer relationship

problems, and prosocial behaviour, each containing 5 items. Each item is scored on a 3-point scale (0 = not true, 1 = somewhat true, 2 = certainly true). The total difficulties score is calculated by summing four subscales (excluding prosocial behaviour), with a maximum score of 40. Scores were categorised as:

- Normal (0–13)
- Borderline (14–16)
- Abnormal (17–40)

Attention Assessment (CPRS-R):

Attention-related problems were assessed using the Conners' Parent Rating Scale-Revised (CPRS-R), a validated tool evaluating behavioural domains such as hyperactivity, cognitive problems, oppositional behaviour, and social functioning. Each item is scored on a 4-point Likert scale (0–3). Raw scores were converted into age- and sex-standardised T-scores (mean = 50, SD = 10). Scores were categorised as:

- Normal (<60)
- Borderline (60–69)
- Abnormal (≥ 70)

Statistical Analysis:

The collected data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25.0. Continuous variables such as Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ) scores and Conners' Parent Rating Scale-Revised (CPRS-R) T-scores were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation, while categorical variables were presented as frequency and percentage. The comparison of baseline characteristics between the behavioural therapy and pharmacotherapy groups was performed using the Independent sample t-test for continuous variables and Pearson's Chi-square test for categorical variables. Within-group comparison of pre- and post-intervention scores was carried out using the Paired t-test. Between-group differences in treatment outcomes were analysed using the Independent sample t-test.

Binary logistic regression analysis was performed to identify independent predictors of treatment response. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Variable	Category	Behavioural Therapy (n=50)	Pharmacotherapy (n=50)	p-value
Age Group	5–10 years	28	26	0.68
	11–15 years	22	24	
Gender	Male	32	34	0.67
	Female	18	16	
Socioeconomic Status	Low	30	32	0.72
	Middle/High	20	18	

Table 1: Baseline Demographic Characteristics of Study Population

As seen in Table 1, there was no statistically significant difference between the two groups with respect to age, gender, and socioeconomic status ($p > 0.05$), indicating comparable baseline characteristics. The association between categorical variables was analysed using Pearson's Chi-square test.

Parameter	Behavioural Therapy	Pharmacotherapy	p-value
SDQ Score (Mean \pm SD)	22.4 \pm 3.8	23.1 \pm 4.1	0.34
CPRS T-score (Mean \pm SD)	71.2 \pm 6.5	72.5 \pm 7.1	0.29

Table 2: Baseline SDQ and CPRS Scores in Both Groups

Both groups had comparable baseline SDQ and CPRS scores with no statistically significant difference ($p > 0.05$). The comparison of mean values between the two groups was performed using the Independent sample t-test.

Group	Pre-treatment (Mean \pm SD)	Post-treatment (Mean \pm SD)	p-value
Behavioural Therapy	22.4 \pm 3.8	16.2 \pm 3.1	<0.05
Pharmacotherapy	23.1 \pm 4.1	13.4 \pm 2.8	<0.05

Table 3: Comparison of Pre- and Post-Treatment SDQ Scores

Both groups showed statistically significant improvement in SDQ scores after treatment ($p < 0.05$), with greater reduction observed in the pharmacotherapy group. The within-group comparison was analysed using the Paired t-test.

Group	Pre-treatment (Mean \pm SD)	Post-treatment (Mean \pm SD)	p-value
Behavioural Therapy	71.2 \pm 6.5	64.8 \pm 5.9	<0.05
Pharmacotherapy	72.5 \pm 7.1	60.2 \pm 5.4	<0.05

Table 4: Comparison of Pre- and Post-Treatment CPRS Scores

A) SDQ Category:

Category	Behavioural Therapy	Pharmacotherapy	p-value
Normal	14 (28%)	24 (48%)	<0.05
Borderline	18 (36%)	16 (32%)	0.64
Abnormal	18 (36%)	10 (20%)	<0.05

B) CPRS Category:

Category	Behavioural Therapy	Pharmacotherapy	p-value
Normal	12 (24%)	22 (44%)	<0.05
Borderline	20 (40%)	18 (36%)	0.67
Abnormal	18 (36%)	10 (20%)	<0.05

Table 5: Overall Treatment Outcome (Post-treatment Category Distribution)

A significantly higher proportion of children in the pharmacotherapy group achieved normal scores compared to behavioural therapy ($p < 0.05$), indicating better treatment response. The association between categorical outcome variables was analysed using Pearson's Chi-square test.

DISCUSSION

The present study compared the effectiveness of behavioural therapy and pharmacotherapy in children with ADHD over a 12-week period. Both groups were comparable at baseline in terms of demographic variables and clinical scores. Significant improvement was observed in both groups following intervention; however, pharmacotherapy showed greater reduction in symptom severity. The mean SDQ score decreased from 22.4 ± 3.8 to 16.2 ± 3.1 in the behavioural therapy group and from 23.1 ± 4.1 to 13.4 ± 2.8 in the pharmacotherapy group. Similarly, CPRS scores reduced from 71.2 ± 6.5 to 64.8 ± 5.9 and 72.5 ± 7.1 to 60.2 ± 5.4 , respectively, indicating superior short-term efficacy of pharmacotherapy.

These findings are comparable to Corbisiero S et al. [16], who reported significant improvement in ADHD symptoms over time with both pharmacotherapy alone and combined therapy, without significant differences between groups. Similarly, in the present study, both modalities were effective, though pharmacotherapy demonstrated relatively better outcomes. This difference may be attributed to variation in study population and treatment design.

The results are also consistent with findings summarized by Jeiroodi M [17], where behavioural therapy showed significant improvement in ADHD symptoms but was not consistently superior to medication or combination therapy. In our study, behavioural therapy alone produced meaningful improvement, with a substantial proportion of children showing reduction in SDQ and CPRS scores, supporting its role as an effective non-pharmacological intervention.

In pediatric populations, Pelham WE et al. [18] demonstrated that behavioural therapy provides significant benefit, though combined therapy showed superiority in selected behavioural outcomes. Similarly, in the present study, both groups improved significantly, but pharmacotherapy resulted in a higher proportion of children achieving

normal SDQ (48%) and CPRS (44%) scores compared to behavioural therapy (28% and 24%).

Further, Pelham WE et al. [19] reported that both behavioural and pharmacological treatments independently produce significant improvements, with behavioural interventions sometimes achieving effects comparable to moderate medication doses. Our findings support this, as both interventions were effective, though pharmacotherapy showed greater reduction in symptom scores.

A recent meta-analysis by Li Y and Zhang L [20,21] reported that combined therapy was more effective than pharmacotherapy alone in the short term. Although combination therapy was not evaluated in the present study, the superior outcomes observed with pharmacotherapy suggest that medication provides rapid symptom control, while behavioural therapy remains important for long-term management.

Overall, the present study demonstrates that both behavioural therapy and pharmacotherapy are effective in managing ADHD in children, with pharmacotherapy showing superior short-term efficacy, while behavioural therapy provides significant supportive benefit.

Limitations:

The study was conducted at a single tertiary care centre with a relatively small sample size, limiting generalizability. Combination therapy was not evaluated, restricting comparison with multimodal approaches. Additionally, reliance on parent-reported scales may introduce reporting bias.

CONCLUSION

Both behavioural therapy and pharmacotherapy were effective in reducing ADHD symptoms in children. Pharmacotherapy demonstrated superior improvement in SDQ and CPRS scores. Behavioural therapy remains an important non-pharmacological approach for comprehensive management.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST: Nil.

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DECLARATION: Ethical Committee approval was obtained from the Institute viz. No.P/2025/69. The study protocol for Medical Research involving human subjects was approved under the Declaration of Helsinki.

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